

OptimESM

Optimal high resolution **Earth System Models**
for exploring future climate change

D5.1 Early warnings for abrupt changes and tipping points

Lead contributor: University of Exeter

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Lead author:	Chris Boulton and Paul Ritchie (University of Exeter)
Contributing authors:	Timothy Lenton (University of Exeter).

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1. Abstract

This deliverable tests the applicability of using early-warning signals as a method for providing forewarning of upcoming abrupt climate shifts that may be associated with tipping points. Two commonly used generic early warning signals, designed to detect critical slowing down prior to a tipping point, are to observe an increase in autocorrelation and variance. We assess the reliability and performance of these indicators prior to a range of abrupt shifts in the latest generation of climate models (CMIP6). These include abrupt shifts in the subpolar gyre in the Atlantic Ocean, in polar sea-ice, and in the Amazon rainforest, which occur under different future climate change scenarios. The analysis is performed on a range of spatial scales, varying from the regional to the grid cell level and new methods are developed to identify clustered regions to monitor. Where generic indicators perform poorly, we consider the potential for system specific indicators. We find statistically significant early warning of abrupt shifts in the subpolar gyre when monitoring ocean streamfunction over a large area of the circulation. We also find system-specific early warning indicators of abrupt loss of parts of the Amazon rainforest.

2. Executive summary

This deliverable describes the work carried out in WP5, Tasks 5.1b & 5.1c specifically, to establish if and where there are early warning signals of tipping points prior to abrupt shifts in CMIP6 model runs. We cannot be sure that all abrupt shifts are associated with underlying tipping points, so the analysis could be viewed as a test of the hypothesis that they are. We explored a range of methods to detect abrupt shifts (in a number of variables), to cluster grid cells from model runs that show similar abrupt shift behaviour (based on time and intensity of abrupt change), and to create early warning signals (and measure their significance). Here we focus on 3 types of abrupt shift with the potential for underlying tipping points: North Atlantic subpolar gyre (SPG) collapse, abrupt changes in polar sea-ice, and abrupt loss of the Amazon rainforest.

Generally, we find that our detection and clustering algorithm works well and is able to find regions that exhibit abrupt changes that are spatially coherent, despite not using any spatial information in our clustering. For our early warning signal analysis, we explore different variables describing the system in question. We analyse both the individual grid cells, as well as the average of the variable of these tipping regions to create time series of the systems. Using these, we measure changes in generic early warning signals (changes in lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and variance), which estimate the occurrence of critical slowing down, a phenomenon which is expected to occur prior to a tipping point.

Results from the SPG collapse analysis suggest that temperature, at least in the models, provides little early warning signal of a collapse. Instead, using the barotropic streamfunction provides better evidence prior to a collapse. Analysis concerning changes in the polar regions shows that the variance tends to provide a statistically significant increasing signal, however the lag-1 autocorrelation provides less conclusive results. For sea-ice loss we find that 80% of the simulations show an increasing trend in early warning indicators, however only half of these become statistically significant before the abrupt shift. One particular model also features abrupt changes in the net downward heat flux and ocean temperature in Antarctica under different climate scenarios. Yet, no consistent patterns emerge, the lag-1 autocorrelation increases for one scenario but shows no trend for the other scenario, in both variables. Testing generic early warning signals prior to Amazon rainforest loss shows that these generic early warning signals are not as robust as using a system specific indicator, measuring the net ecosystem productivity (NEP) sensitivity to temperature anomalies.

These results provide guidance on where early warning signals could be searched for in the real world, particularly for the SPG collapse (looking for signals from the barotropic streamfunction rather than temperature) and the Amazon rainforest (looking at more specific early warning signals).

3. Work carried out

Work for this deliverable has focussed on analysing the applicability of generic and system specific early warning signals of tipping points prior to abrupt shifts in CMIP6 model output. Novel approaches have been developed, and a range of recognised tipping elements of the Earth system considered. In particular, early warning signals have been tested on output variables of CMIP6 models relating to a collapse of the North Atlantic subpolar gyre, abrupt changes in polar regions (such as sea-ice loss), and dieback of the Amazon rainforest. The main results of this work is presented in the next section, but in the following we describe the main methods used to carry out this analysis.

Detection algorithm: Due to the volume of data available to analyse, an automated approach is required to identify the model grid cells that feature abrupt transitions. We therefore employ the abrupt shift detection algorithm introduced by Boulton & Lenton (2019) that looks for anomalous rates of change in state variables. This is performed by splitting the time series into lots of small segments and fitting a linear regression within each segment. The gradients are recorded, and those that fall outside three median absolute deviations from the median of gradients are identified as being anomalous. All time points within these segments are then determined to feature an abrupt transition. This process is then repeated iteratively for different sized segment lengths, starting from segments featuring just 5 data points up until only 3 segments cover the full time series. The proportion of occasions that individual time points are identified as featuring an anomalous rate of change is used to build a detection time series. The peak of the detection time series corresponds to the time of the largest abrupt change detected in the time series. The closer the peak value is to +1 (-1) the more abrupt the increase (decrease) in the variable of interest is.

Note that this detection algorithm differs from the one used by KNMI (Milestone number 12, Detection and attribution of tipping points performed on CMIP6 ESMs). All detection methods have their advantages (and disadvantages) and all methods might miss some examples of tipping points and thresholds for detection are rather arbitrarily. Thus, we think it makes more sense to compare the results from the different detection methods than using only one detection method.

Clustering of grid cells: We cluster grid cells that display similar abrupt shift characteristics. Specifically, grid cells are clustered using a K-means clustering approach based on the largest minimum or maximum value of the detection time series and the year of this occurrence. Importantly, no spatial geographic metric is used for the clustering, yet spatially coherent regions are still identified. We use the 'elbow method' to determine the number of clusters to use, which looks to optimise the within-sum-of-squares (WSS) such that additional clusters provide diminishing returns. While this is usually done by eye, we have created an algorithm that automatically selects this optimal number of clusters, by looking for a drop in WSS that is less than 30%. This automation appears to match up well with what we observe by eye.

Generic early warning signals: Early warning indicators are derived for time series from individual grid cells, from predefined regions, and from the uniquely defined regions derived from the clustering. Two commonly used early warning signals to try and detect an upcoming tipping point are to see an increase in both the lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and variance. These signals are calculated on the detrended time series up until the detected abrupt change (as they assume stationarity). The time series are first detrended using a Gaussian kernel with a carefully chosen bandwidth to ensure that any long term trends are removed, but higher frequency fluctuations that the theory is based on, remain. Similarly, the early warning signals are calculated over a sliding window that is chosen short enough so that the system can be assumed to be approximately stationary and a trend can be sufficiently derived, but long enough to estimate the metric (i.e. systems with slow timescales need longer windows). We use two methods for quantifying the trend in an early warning signal, the first is to calculate the Kendall tau value. The Kendall tau value gives an indication of how much a time series is either increasing (values close to +1) or decreasing (values close to -1). Alternatively, we identify when any trend in the signal is statistically significant. That is, we define a 95% confidence interval that the signal would reside in without forcing, and consider that exceeding this interval represents a

statistically significant trend. The interval is determined from the pre-industrial control runs and is ± 1 standard error (i.e. square root of the variance of the signal) multiplied by the 95% quantile of a Gaussian distribution.

System specific early warning signals: For the Amazon rainforest tipping point analysis specifically, we also test a system specific indicator, namely the sensitivity of net ecosystem productivity (NEP) to temperature anomalies, following work from (Boulton et al., 2013). An increase in this sensitivity suggests the forest is under stress as larger temperature anomalies will lead to stronger decreases in NEP. The sensitivity is calculated by fitting a linear regression model on the NEP time series, using the temperature time series as an explanatory variable, once both have been detrended as described in the section above. This sensitivity is taken to be the linear coefficient of this regression, which is calculated on a moving window much like the generic early warning signals detailed above, with the Kendall tau value providing an indication of whether or not the sensitivity is increasing or not.

4. Main results - Early warning indicators

i. North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre (SPG) collapse

Previously, a selection of CMIP6 models have been identified to project a collapse of deep convection in the North Atlantic subpolar gyre (SPG) under future climate change scenarios (Swingedouw et al., 2021). We use the same models and Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios, although we only use 1 experiment per modelling centre, and so we chose CESM2-WACCM under SSP126 which has the most pronounced collapse of the SPG. We seek to determine if there are early warning signals before the abrupt shifts in the models. Figure 1 provides an insight into the projected impacts of an SPG collapse over the North Atlantic. A key signature of an SPG collapse is a cooling over the North Atlantic and western Europe. Panel (a) shows the ensemble mean change in surface air temperature between the 20 years after and the 20 years preceding the detected tipping of the SPG for the three simulations of climate models and future climate scenarios. On the other hand, a small warming is projected over North America and the subtropical Atlantic. The drop in temperature across the North Atlantic coincides with a freshening of the sea surface, and equivalently the warming with an increase in salinity, see panel (b). In regions of deep convection around the southern tip of Greenland, the mixed layer depth shallows by as much as 200m, but further south there is little change (as indicated by the stippling), see panel (c). Panel (d) shows that the models project the ocean barotropic streamfunction (the depth integrated transport of water) to increase in the northern Atlantic but to decrease for a band of water further south.

Figure 1: Projected impacts of a subpolar gyre collapse. Ensemble mean changes for 20-year means following and preceding a collapse of the subpolar gyre (SPG) for: (a) surface air temperature (b) sea surface salinity, (c) mixed layer depth, (d) Ocean barotropic streamfunction. Models, scenarios and year of collapse of SPG used in the ensemble are: NorESM2-LM, ssp126, 2035; CESM2-WACCM, ssp126, 2040; MRI-ESM2-0, ssp245, 2040. Stippling indicates regions where models fail to agree on the sign change of the respective variable following an SPG collapse. Black box indicates the region in which an area weighted average is calculated for relevant variables of the SPG. All models are put onto a uniform $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid using the closest neighbour.

The black box depicted in the Figure 1 panels has previously been used to calculate an area weighted mean for key variables that indicate the behaviour of the SPG. This captures regions of large change in sea surface temperature, salinity, and barotropic streamfunction, but misses regions of greatest change in mixed layer depth. Time series for the temperature in this box is given in Figure 2(a) for each of the three simulations. Here we see clear abrupt shifts in the temperature for each of the simulations as highlighted by the detection time series in panel (b). The shifts occur around the middle of the 21st century. In NorESM2-LM under the SSP126 scenario two abrupt shifts are detected, the second less significant than the first. In our analysis however, we use the largest detected shift each time.

Figure 2: Lack of early-warning signals in temperature preceding a subpolar gyre collapse. (a) Time series of an area weighted mean over the North Atlantic for change in surface air temperature from 1850 in the three studied simulations. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over temperature time series presented in (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 100 years on the temperature time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal.

Calculating the early warning indicators (increasing lag-1 autocorrelation (AR1) and variance) on the time series data given in panel (a) offers little indication of the upcoming abrupt shifts. NorESM2-LM provides the best signal with variance providing a significant signal (by exceeding a 95% confidence interval indicated by the banding) and the AR(1) momentarily rising about the confidence interval. The remaining simulations also show an increasing AR(1) signal (albeit not always significant), however, the variance tends to decrease and therefore fail to provide early warning.

Figure 3(a) displays the area averaged change in the North Atlantic box (depicted in Figure 1(d)) of the ocean barotropic streamfunction (depth integrated volume transport of water) from 1850 for the three simulations. The mechanism leading to a subpolar gyre collapse is related to the collapse of deep convection in the subpolar gyre, modifying profoundly the oceanic circulation, which manifests itself as changes in the barotropic streamfunction (Swingedouw et al. 2021). Two of the three simulations show an abrupt increase

near the beginning of the 21st century. Whereas, the MRI-ESM2-0 simulation (green) shows an initial decline followed by a gradual increase during the 20th century. The streamfunction then drops noticeably sharply at the beginning of the 21st century before slowly increasing again. The lack of the streamfunction ever appearing to be in steady state means that the detection algorithm fails to identify an abrupt change occurring, note the minimum value is only about -0.1 and is near the beginning of the run, see panel (b). Consequently, the early warning signals are only performed on the other two simulations. The CESM2-WACCM simulation provides statistically significant signals in both the AR(1) (panel (c)) and variance (panel (d)) preceding the abrupt change and therefore suggest early warning would be possible. For NorESM2-LM the AR(1) shows a statistically significant increasing trend, however the variance shows little change overall and therefore no warning is provided.

Figure 3: Performance of early-warning signals in ocean barotropic streamfunction preceding a subpolar gyre collapse. (a) Time series of a normalised area weighted mean over the North Atlantic for change in ocean barotropic streamfunction from 1850 in the three studied simulations. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over ocean barotropic streamfunction time series presented in (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 100 years on the ocean barotropic streamfunction time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum/maximum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal.

Figure 3: Performance of early-warning signals in ocean barotropic streamfunction preceding a subpolar gyre collapse.

(a) Time series of a normalised area weighted mean over the North Atlantic for change in ocean barotropic streamfunction from 1850 in the three studied simulations. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over ocean barotropic streamfunction time series presented in (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 100 years on the ocean barotropic streamfunction time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum/maximum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal.

As an alternative approach, we identify grid cells that have similar abrupt shift characteristics, rather than use a pre-defined region, and test the early warning signals on these uniquely defined regions. Here we will specifically focus on the barotropic streamfunction. We cluster grid cells based on the largest minimum or maximum value of the detection time series and the year of this occurrence. Importantly, no spatial geographic metric is used for the clustering, yet coherent spatial regions are recovered (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Early warnings for abrupt changes and tipping points

Figure 4: Clustering of grid cells using abrupt shift characteristics for ocean barotropic streamfunction. Colour plots of: (a), (d), (g) largest value of detection time series (maximum or minimum) after running abrupt shift detection algorithm; (b), (e), (h) year of detected abrupt shift (time of largest value of detection time series); (c), (f), (i) clustered grid cells based on statistics from the two panels above. (a) - (c) NorESM2-LM, SSP126; (d) - (f) CESM2-WACCM, SSP126; (g) - (i) MRI-ESM2-0, SSP245.

Many grid cells in the NorESM2-LM simulation experience a relatively strong abrupt shift in the ocean barotropic streamfunction as shown by Figure 4(a). The subpolar gyre region undergoes an abrupt increase in the streamfunction (blue points), whereas, further south the streamfunction abruptly decreases (red points). The increasing abrupt shifts tend to occur slightly later than the decreasing abrupt shifts, see Figure 4(b). Figure 4(c) shows the clustering using these two metrics and despite the lack of a spatial clustering metric two coherent and distinct regions have been successfully identified (blue and orange clusters) corresponding to the contrasting types of abrupt shift. A third cluster (green) is also identified, which largely groups the grid cells that do not undergo an abrupt transition. The CESM2-WACCM simulation identifies similar behaviour (Figure 4(d)-(f)). A subpolar gyre cluster consisting of increasing abrupt changes in the streamfunction and the orange cluster featuring decreasing abrupt changes. This orange cluster still includes a strip south of the subpolar gyre region but also includes many coastal points down eastern America and western Europe. The green cluster again represents grid cells without large abrupt changes. In contrast, the MRI-ESM2-0 simulation identifies less notable abrupt changes. Two small regions of abrupt decline in the streamfunction are identified in the central eastern side of the Atlantic. Despite the northern region undergoing an abrupt change considerably earlier than the southern, these two regions combined make up the green cluster. The other two clusters (blue and orange) are mainly separated based on the timing of the maximum or minimum in the detection time series (panel (h)), despite not really featuring prominent abrupt changes.

Figure 5 displays the time series and early warning signals for these clustered regions. Recall for the NorESM2-LM and CESM2-WACCM simulations the blue cluster features an increasing abrupt change in the streamfunction while the orange decreases abruptly. Running the detection algorithm on these averaged time series (panels (a) and (e)) identifies these abrupt changes in the first half of the 21st century (panels (b) and (f)). Note, the green clusters, which largely contain grid cells with no abrupt changes, still feature no abrupt changes after averaging over the cluster. Therefore, we evaluate the performance of the early warning signals on the blue and orange clusters in panels (c), (d), (g), (h) in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Early warning signals in ocean barotropic streamfunction for clustered regions. (a), (e), (i) Time series of normalised ocean barotropic streamfunction for clusters identified in Figure 4. (b), (f), (j) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over ocean barotropic streamfunction time series presented in panels above to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c), (g), (k) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d), (h), (l) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 100 years ((k) and (l) are calculated over sliding windows of length 50 years) on the ocean barotropic streamfunction time series in (a), (e), (i) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum/maximum of the detection time series in (b), (f), (j). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (a) - (d) NorESM2-LM, SSP126; (e) - (h) CESM2-WACCM, SSP126; (i) - (l) MRI-ESM2-0, SSP245.

For the CESM2-WACCM simulation (panels (g) and (h)) both clusters, the AR(1) and variance both display an increasing trend. Moreover, the indicators exceed a 95% confidence interval (indicated by the banding and determined from an unforced control simulation), and thus give a significant signal to offer forewarning of the upcoming abrupt transitions. The NorESM2-LM simulation also generally shows an increasing trend in the early warning signals for the blue and orange clusters (panels (c) and (d)). The blue cluster does also give a statistically significant signal. The AR(1) gives an early statistically significant signal, however, the variance only rises very late and this is likely due to not detrending properly. This is because the abrupt shift has already started, while noting the detection algorithm identifies the point in time of the largest change, not necessarily the beginning of the abrupt change. For the orange cluster both the AR(1) and variance show increasing trends, but, despite a momentary exceedance of the variance interval, fail to provide a statistically significant signal.

Running the detection algorithm on the time series clusters for the MRI-ESM2-0 simulation all show an increasing abrupt change in the streamfunction in the historical period. This is particularly surprising for the green cluster given it predominantly featuring grid cells with decreasing abrupt changes. Though the two small regions of decreasing abrupt changes occur at different time intervals, one at the beginning and the other in the second half of the 21st century. Therefore, averaging across these regions smooths out the time series and another abrupt shift is detected in the 20th century instead. The orange cluster abrupt shift features in the second half of the 20th century and therefore with a smaller sliding window (50 years) we are able to calculate the early warning signals for this cluster. Here, both the AR(1) and variance show strongly increasing trends that both comfortably exceed the banding and therefore provide sufficient early warning for this abrupt change.

ii. Abrupt changes in polar regions

Work in Task 5.1a, performed by KNMI, has involved searching for abrupt changes in the CMIP6 models under various future climate change scenarios. The initial results of this have revealed many abrupt changes in different ocean variables that are particularly found in the polar regions. The regions cover at least a million square kilometres and are uniquely defined by their algorithm (different to Boulton & Lenton, 2019) used to detect abrupt changes. In the following, and as part of Task 5.1b, we test the generic early warning signals on some of these examples to determine if any warning would be possible.

Figure 6(a) shows five simulations, from different models and SSPs, of abrupt changes in sea ice concentration. The regions these time series correspond to are shown by the maps in panels (e) and (f). Panel (b) displays the detection time series, with all simulations (apart from CanESM5) reaching a peak below -0.6. The generic early warning signals are given in panels (c) (AR(1)) and (d) (variance).

All but one (GISS-E2-1-H, SSP126) provide a statistically significant signal in the variance before the abrupt change occurs. However, the AR(1) signal is much less robust across the simulations. Note the GISS-E2-1-H, SSP126 simulation also fails to provide any trend in the AR(1) as well. The most promising example comes from the HadGEM3-GC31-MM model under the SSP585 scenario for sea ice loss in the Antarctic. Here, the AR(1) increases early and exceeds, and remains above, the confidence interval more than 100 years before the abrupt change. The variance also exceeds the interval early, and despite a momentary return to the interval does remain continually above the interval for roughly 50 years preceding the abrupt shift. Therefore, suggesting that early warning of this abrupt shift would be possible. Similarly, the GISS-E2-1-H, SSP119 example in the Arctic displays similar behaviour, but the continual exceedance of the interval only occurs just before the abrupt shift (see green curve in panel (c)). The remaining simulations (CanESM5 and GISS-E2-1-H both under the SSP245 scenario) show (at least late) increases in the AR(1) before the abrupt shift but not sufficiently enough to provide a statistically significant signal.

Figure 6: Early warning signals for sea ice loss. (a) Time series of simulations displaying an abrupt shift in sea ice concentration. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over sea ice concentration time series presented in panel (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 50 years on the sea ice concentration time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (e) and (f) maps showing areas of abrupt shifts found in the sea ice concentration. Colours in all panels correspond to the model and scenario given by the legend in panel (b).

control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (e) and (f) maps showing areas of abrupt shifts found in the sea ice concentration. Colours in all panels correspond to the model and scenario given by the legend in panel (b).

We have just seen that the GISS-E2-1-H model under two different climate scenarios projects abrupt sea ice loss on the eastern side of Antarctica. Two other variables, the net downward heat flux and ocean temperature, are also projected to undergo abrupt transitions in a similar region for the GISS-E2-1-H model under various climate scenarios. First, Figure 7 studies the net downward heat flux. Panel (a) shows two time series displaying abrupt declines in the net downward heat flux in the second half of the 21st century. These are highlighted by the detection time series in panel (b) giving clear minima that are both below -0.5. The variance (panel (d)) for both simulations provide statistically significant increasing trends about 50 years prior to the respective abrupt changes. However, the AR(1) signal (panel (c)) is less conclusive. On the one hand, after an initial drop the AR(1) consistently increases and does provide a statistically significant signal and so early warning would in theory be possible for the SSP126 scenario (blue). On the other hand, the more extreme climate scenario, SSP585, the AR(1) shows no trend and therefore no early warning. Note that while there are good reasons to believe that net surface downward heat flux or ocean temperature are closely related to sea ice changes, we here only detect that that these abrupt changes occur in the same region. To really link these abrupt changes and generalise the results from this section, further research would be required.

Figure 7: Early warning signals for net downward heat flux. (a) Time series of simulations displaying an abrupt shift in net downward heat flux. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over net downward heat flux time series presented in panel (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 50 years on the net downward heat flux time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the minimum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (e) and (f) maps showing areas of abrupt shifts found in the net downward heat flux. Colours in all panels correspond to the model and scenario given by the legend in panel (b).

indicates a 95% confidence interval, calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (e) and (f) maps showing areas of abrupt shifts found in the net downward heat flux. Colours in all panels correspond to the model and scenario given by the legend in panel (b).

Finally Figure 8 provides two examples of abrupt changes in the surface ocean temperature from the GISS-E2-1-H model. In both examples in panel (a), the ocean temperature abruptly increases by about 3°C at the end of the 21st century. Again, clear maxima, with values greater than 0.6, are identified in the detection time series, signifying these abrupt changes, see panel (b). Similar to the net downward heat flux, the variance (panel (d)) for both simulations of the ocean temperature provide statistically significant trends but the AR(1) (panel (c)) gives mixed results. On this occasion, it is the more extreme climate scenario (SSP370) that provides a statistically significant signal, that coupled with the variance signal could provide early warning by more than 50 years. Yet, the SSP126 simulation does not produce a trend in the AR(1) and therefore early warning would not be possible for this example. Note also the regional area size does not appear to be a determining factor of whether early warning is possible. For instance, in the ocean temperature the smaller region provides the early warning (Figure 8(f)), however, for the net downward heat flux, it is the larger area that gives early warning and the smaller area does not (Figure 7(f)).

Figure 8: Early warning signals for surface ocean temperature. (a) Time series of simulations displaying an abrupt shift in surface ocean temperature. (b) Detection time series generated from abrupt shift detection algorithm performed over surface ocean temperature time series presented in panel (a) to indicate location of abrupt shifts. (c) Lag-1 autocorrelation (AR(1)) and (d) variance calculated over a sliding window of length 50 years on the surface ocean temperature time series in (a) until the detected abrupt shift as determined by the maximum of the detection time series in (b). Banding indicates a 95% confidence interval,

calculated from pre-industrial control runs, that the early warning signals fluctuate within. Exceeding this banding above would therefore provide a statistically significant signal. (e) and (f) maps showing areas of abrupt shifts found in the surface ocean temperature. Colours in all panels correspond to the model and scenario given by the legend in panel (b).

iii. Amazon rainforest dieback

A lot of our analysis of the Amazon rainforest is dependent on what is readily available on CMIP6 data nodes. We use the carbon stored in vegetation (cVeg) as the variable to determine the presence of rainforest in the models, and look within the region 80°-45°W, 20°S-10°N. We begin our analysis by looking into some of the CMIP6 1% CO₂ runs (1pctCO₂), including those tested by Parry et al., (2022) which are forced by increasing CO₂ by 1% a year. When clustering the results from the detection algorithm on the cVeg time series in the TaiESM1 1pctCO₂ run, we find a distinct area that exhibits abrupt shift behaviour (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Clustering of detection algorithm on the TaiESM1 1pctCO₂ cVeg time series. (a) The max detection value and the year detected show 4 clusters (shown by different colours). Centres of each cluster are shown as a closed circle of the colour of the cluster. (b) Spatial distribution of the clusters, showing a clear region that exhibits an abrupt shift according to (a). (c) Time series of cVeg (kg C/m²), calculated as the mean from the clusters.

We look specifically at the generic early warning signals (Fig. 10) that are found using the mean cVeg time series that exhibits the abrupt shift (Fig. 9c), using the detection algorithm on these mean time series to determine a cut off point.

Figure 10: Generic early warning signals tested on the TaiESM1 cVeg Amazon region cluster that exhibits an abrupt shift in Fig. 9. (a) The time series of mean cVeg from the cluster (purple in Fig. 9c). The full time series (grey) is shown alongside the time series used in the early warning signal analysis (black), with the cutoff position determined by running the detection algorithm on the time series. After detrending and using a moving window equal to 50 years, we calculate the (b) AR(1) and (c) variance indicators on this time series.

Despite the detection algorithm cutoff including part of the decline (Fig. 10a), there is a clear increase in both indicators even before the sharp increase in them (Fig. 10b,c). We now turn our attention to the individual grid cells that create that cluster, seeing if generic early warning signals can be observed at local scale. To do this, we use the detected time of tipping from our detection algorithm for each grid cell that is in the cluster and calculate the AR(1) and variance time series on a window length of 50 years (those where the detected tipping is within the first 50 years are not used in the analysis). We then calculate the Kendall tau of each of these time series (Fig. 11). This shows that although variance works reasonably well, AR(1) appears to be a poor indicator of predicting the movement of the individual grid cells towards tipping.

Figure 11: Histograms of Kendall tau values from the generic early warning indicators for individual grid cells that make up the cluster that exhibits the abrupt shift in Fig. 9. (a) AR(1) and (b) variance tendencies are calculated as described in the main text. Values near 1 suggest an indication towards tipping.

With AR(1) failing to indicate the movement towards tipping, we look to the system specific indicator of NEP sensitivity (the calculation of which is described in the Methods section). Indeed, for the individual grid cells that make up the cluster that shows abrupt shifts, we find strong negative Kendall tau values generally (Fig. 12a). Furthermore, it also shows a strong signal of an increase in NEP sensitivity for the mean cluster overall too.

Figure 12: Signals from NEP sensitivity in the Amazon region of the TaiESM1 1pctCO₂ run. (a) Kendall tau values from the individual grid cells that make up the cluster that exhibits the abrupt shift in Fig. 9. (b) The mean time series of cVeg from that cluster (as in Fig. 9c). (c) The NEP sensitivity time series from the cluster.

To determine how NEP sensitivity changes when the forest is not being forced, we look to the TaiESM1 piControl model, where forcings are kept constant and the model behaves like an equilibrium simulation. Our abrupt shift detection and clustering combination finds no obvious shifts in vegetation as expected (Fig. 13). Using all the land grid cells regardless of cluster, we calculate both generic early warning signals, and NEP sensitivity. using data up to the maximum abrupt shift detection (in most cases this is small). Figure 13d-f shows that there is no obvious trend in signal.

Figure 13: Signals from generic early warning signals and NEP sensitivity in the Amazon region of the TaiESM1 piControl run. (a) The max detection value and the year detected show 4 clusters (shown by different colours). Centres of each cluster are shown as a closed circle of the colour of the cluster. (b) Spatial distribution of the clusters. (c) Time series of cVeg, calculated as the mean from the clusters, showing that there are none that exhibit an abrupt shift. (d)-(f) Histograms of Kendall tau values from all individual land grid cell time series for AR(1), variance and NEP sensitivity respectively.

We also have begun to analyse output from the SSP scenarios. The caveat with these is that they include land use change, which may cause abrupt shifts in vegetation which would otherwise be undetectable due to their sudden, unforced nature. Again using TaiESM1, we analyse the SSP scenario simulations (SSP126, 245, 370, and 585). Clustering reveals regions that show abrupt shifts much like the 1pctCO2 run (Fig. 14). Time series of the clusters clearly show clusters that exhibit tipping in the stronger-forcing SSP scenarios (370 and 585). Importantly, we find no obvious shifts in land use change, particularly decreases in tree cover that would explain these abrupt shifts.

Figure 14: Results from clustering analysis in the Amazon region of the TaiESM1 SSPs run. (a)-(d) The max detection value and the year detected show 4 clusters (shown by different colours). Centres of each cluster are shown as a closed circle of the colour of the cluster. (e)-(h) Spatial distribution of the clusters (i)-(l) Time series of cVeg, calculated as the mean from the clusters. (m)-(p) The mean tree cover fraction as prescribed by the SSP scenarios, showing no obvious abrupt shifts that would create abrupt shifts in the corresponding cVeg time series.

We again use the detection algorithm to cut the mean cluster time series pre-tipping (vertical lines in Fig. 14i-l) and test both the generic early warning signals and NEP sensitivities in these clusters (Fig. 15), this time using a window length of 20 years due to the shorter time series compared to the 1pctCO2 run. Here, we find that the generic early warning signals appear to fail, whereas the NEP sensitivity appears to increase before shifts. We note here that abrupt shifts are not observed in all cluster time series but we show them here for completeness.

Figure 15: Results from clustering analysis in the Amazon region of the TaiESM1 SSPs run, following on from Fig. 14. (a)-(d) AR(1), (e)-(h) variance, and (i)-(l) NEP sensitivity calculated on the mean cluster time series shown in Fig. 14, after detrending as described in the Methods section, and using a window length of 20 years. Signals are not calculated if the detected shift occurs within the first 20 years (vertical lines in Fig. 14i-l).

5. Impact beyond the state-of-the-art

Early warning signals have recently gained increasing attention as a method for providing some forewarning of an upcoming tipping point (Scheffer et al., 2009; Bury et al., 2021). Generic early warning signals (e.g. increasing AR(1) and variance) have been developed based on a system experiencing *critical slowing down* before reaching a tipping point (Lenton et al., 2012). These early warning signals have been applied to observations (Dakos et al., 2008; Boulton et al., 2022), and in the full hierarchy of models (Williamson et al., 2016; Clarke et al., 2023; van Westen et al., 2024).

Here we go beyond the current state-of-the-art by applying them to abrupt shifts found in the latest generation of Earth System Models (CMIP6). Furthermore, we not only consider generic early warning signals but also system specific signals for the Amazon rainforest. We apply these early warning signals both on regional scales and the grid cell level. Importantly, for the first time we also apply the early warning signals to unique regions that have been identified from a clustering analysis that considers grid cells with similar abrupt shift characteristics.

We find mixed results, which may be expected as it is not established whether abrupt shifts in the CMIP6 models reflect underlying bifurcation tipping points that would be expected to show critical slowing down beforehand. We find cases of abrupt shifts in the models with statistically significant generic early warning signals beforehand, which can be taken as support for the hypothesis of an underlying tipping point. They pose some additional challenges for realising early warning in reality, in particular the challenge of identifying in advance the appropriate 'cluster' regions in which to look for early warning signals.

6. Contribution to OptimESM's objectives

The results discussed in this deliverable primarily contribute to Objective 5: *To increase our understanding of potential tipping points in the Earth system.* Specifically, using ESM output we have increased our understanding of the potential for observing early warning signals prior to abrupt shifts in a variety of systems. For example, we have shown that despite air temperature being a key signature of a subpolar gyre deep convection collapse, the generic early warning signals tend to not perform well on temperature. However, more success can be achieved by using the depth integrated volume transport of water (ocean barotropic streamfunction). In the Amazon rainforest, system specific early warning signals (as opposed to the generic early warning signals) appear to work best. Namely, we find that the sensitivity of net ecosystem productivity (NEP) to temperature decreases markedly in grid cells that feature abrupt shifts. Whereas, the generic early warning signals, the lag-1 autocorrelation particularly, fail to provide a robust trend.

7. Lessons learnt and links built

We have found that some variables appear to provide more robust early warning signals of abrupt shifts than others. In particular, ocean barotropic streamfunction provides a more robust early warning signal than temperature for an abrupt shift in the SPG, despite temperature being a clear signature of abrupt change. This could be a result of temperature being subjected to many different processes which hides any critical slowing down signals. Whereas the ocean barotropic streamfunction more directly reflects the circulation itself and unwanted noise processes are smoothed out in the depth integration of transport of water. Furthermore, we have found that individual grid cells and/or clustered grid cells (with similar abrupt shift characteristics) provide better early warning than large generic rectangular areas. However, this poses the challenge of identifying appropriate clusters to monitor in advance of abrupt change (rather than retrospectively, as in our analysis). This may be possible as the clusters that emerge for the SPG appear to be physically based, reflecting the circulation itself.

For our analysis of the Amazon rainforest, we find system specific indicators can provide a more reliable approach to getting early warning than the generic signals. Interestingly, generic early warning signals sometimes appear to work for larger areas for this terrestrial ecosystem compared to the SPG collapse case; they however fail when looking at individual grid cells. In some cases we believe that the timescale of the system could be too slow for generic early warning signals to detect, where system specific indicators are using knowledge about the mechanisms of the system and appear to be less affected by the timescale problem.

In all 3 case studies, we find that our clustering approach, which uses metrics derived from the detection algorithm, works well. However, this method poses an interesting challenge for observing early warning in practice; that is how to identify, in advance, the appropriate clustered regions to monitor. Future work will therefore entail exploring whether similar algorithms can be used to detect clusters based on variability or e.g. circulation patterns for the SPG (as mentioned above), rather than abrupt shift characteristics, such that we can monitor regions without prior knowledge of tipping. This could inform us of specific regions of the corresponding system to monitor for early warning signals in real world observations.

Some of the results presented here have utilised findings from other members of the WP. For instance we have collaborated closely with KNMI, who have provided us with data of the abrupt changes they have identified in Task 5.1a. Consequently, we have used their data to test for the prospect of getting early warning signals before these abrupt changes would occur. This has specifically focussed on analysing many ocean variables (including, but not limited to: ocean temperature, sea ice concentration, mixed layer depth) that undergo abrupt transitions, primarily in the polar regions, and in multiple models and under a range of climate scenarios.

We plan to use the results of Task 5.1 to inform the modelling groups future work in WPs 1-3. For example, we can communicate the abrupt shifts that are found in their model simulation runs and the prospect for early warning under the different climate scenarios. This will help the modelling groups identify the processes that are key for representing abrupt changes and what processes might be missing. In particular, the modelling groups would gain a greater understanding that if increasing the resolution of their model, so that it can capture smaller scale processes, more abrupt changes and/or tipping points would be represented.

8. Potential policy feedback relevance of the deliverable

There is already policy interest in the potential for an early warning system for climate tipping points, and a recent funding call from ARIA in the UK that includes the SPG as a target system for tipping point early warning. Our results suggest there is potential for early warning of an abrupt shift in the subpolar gyre, and they inform the design of an early warning system (accepting that GCMs are an imperfect representation of reality but do capture key processes). In the case of the SPG collapse, our results suggest early warning indicators may not be observable in temperature variables but monitoring should instead focus on the ocean circulation (streamfunction) itself. This has clear design and cost implications since the ocean circulation is less easily observable than the ocean surface temperature. It implies efforts would be needed to reconstruct past streamfunction variability.

Our results also show the potential for system specific early warning indicators of abrupt loss of parts of the Amazon rainforest. Generic early warning indicators based on fluctuations in biomass in the models give mixed results, but they have been observed in reality (Boulton et al., 2022; van Passel et al., 2024.). This may indicate weaknesses in the models' representation of the forest. Nevertheless, the system specific early warning indicators identified can readily be measured. The same mechanisms that show an increase in NEP sensitivity to temperature anomalies should show an increase in CO₂ sensitivity to temperature anomalies which can be measured with (e.g.) flux towers in the rainforest.

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